

Expectations of Students to Improve their Academic Performance - CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Dropping out of school is a real problem, especially among first-year students, both at European and national level. In this context, the purpose of the research was to identify the main factors that determine Romanian students to drop out of college. Based on this results, it was identified solutions, means and tools useful in reducing the high dropout rate and increasing the academic performance of students. An online questionnaire was applied within the project ``*E-tutoring: web tools and resources for study and career management*`` in order to identify the main needs of students. The analysis of the data collected was performed using the Qualitative Content Analysis. The result of the analysis highlighted the fact that the main factors that contribute to school dropout are generated by financial problems, teaching methods, inappropriate choice of specialization and lack of support for counseling. The results demonstrate the need for an innovative system, based on peer learning and a lifelong career approach.

Keywords: career guidance, Cronbach's alpha, students` drop out

Introduction

Romania is the third country in the European Union in terms of early school leaving in education and training systems, for people aged 18-24 (EUROSTAT, 2019). According to data published in the ``Training and Education Monitor, 2019: The report for Romania`` early school leaving (18-24 years) indicates a percentage of 16.4% for young Romanians, compared to an EU average of 10.6%. Also, the share of graduates (30-34 years) is 24.6% for Romania, and the European average is 40.7%.

As noted EUROSTAT (2019), „the largest gender differences among the proportion of young people who were early leavers and not wanting to work were recorded in Romania (6.9 percentage points higher for young women than young men)”. In 2018, Romania registered a high level of early school leaving, of 16.4%, as well as a low rate of the population aged between 30 and 34 who graduated from higher education (24.6%). In light of these data, study success is high on the policy agenda in Europe and one of the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy is that at least 40% of 30-34-year-olds complete higher education.

In recent years, at the national level, the trend of school dropout is increasing and has a significant impact on the unemployment rate and social inclusion. The employment rate among students in Romania, on the age segment of 20-25 years, in the chosen field of study, is well below the European average of 80%. Moreover, the *National Council for Statistics and Forecasting of Higher Education* states that more than 53% of students come from rural and disadvantaged backgrounds. The reasons

why they leave the education system are mainly financial. To these is added the diminished motivation of students to complete their undergraduate university studies.

Although the Europe 2020 program in the field of education and training aims to reduce the number of people leaving the education and training system early below 10%, in recent years, there has been an increasing trend in the drop-out rate at national level. According to U-Multirank, coordinated by the European Commission, the highest dropout rate of students was registered in Romania (U-Multirank 2014), most of them being students enrolled in the first year.

As G. Raftu (2019) said, students choose a faculty at the recommendation of their parents or out of the desire to leave home, being attracted by the “student life”. Most of the time their expectations are not met. The academic and social difficulties they face, the inability to manage time, workload, budget and interpersonal relationships are factors that generate academic dropout.

Studies conducted at national level have shown that Romanian universities are facing a significant decrease in the number of students, especially students enrolled in the first year of college (SAVA S, 2015). The number of students is drastically reduced during the undergraduate studies, only about half of the enrolled students succeed in completing the undergraduate studies. The identification of solutions and measures of educational policy that would lead to the improvement of the phenomenon of decreasing the students' motivation represent objectives that the Romanian universities have assumed.

Numerous projects have been approved at European level, in order to reduce the number of students who do not complete their undergraduate studies. The purpose of the projects are to identify the main factors favoring school dropout and to develop new resources to improve students' academic performance. One such project is E-tutoring. This is a project funded by the Erasmus + program (2018-1-IT02-KA203-048005) that works to reduce academic drop-out rates with the development of a set of tools and a new tutoring system that combine career guidance, peer learning, social networks and new digital technologies (<https://www.etutoring.eu/>). The project consortium involves eight partners from six countries: Romania, Italy, Turkey, Spain, Greece and Lithuania. The partnership wants to create the following resources that will improve the student's academic performance: A research report on Career Management Skills in academic students:

- E-tutoring in Europe, a collection of good practices.
- A methodological framework to guide the design of e-tutoring services.
- E-tutoring App.
- E-learning platform for training tutors.

Research methodology

There are many reasons why students drop out of college, especially in the first year of study. Most of the time, these reasons are complex and interconnected. The main objective of this study was to determine the level of students' satisfaction and identify the difficulties encountered by them, respectively what are the determining causes of dropout, especially for students in year I. Studies on the tendency to drop out and the correlations between factors that determine such decisions have been made in recent years by many researchers. Van Sangodiah (2015) states that the age of students, gender, financial situation, specialization and form of education time management, etc. are factors that contribute to student dropout.

The research results presented in this article were obtained by applying an online questionnaire to students following the bachelor's program in the Faculty of Industrial and Robotic Engineering, within the University Politehnica of Bucharest. The decision to implement the questionnaire at this faculty was based on a study conducted at the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics, on the situation of people who dropped out of undergraduate studies since the first year. According to this study, in the period 2013 - 2014, 112 students dropped out the faculty, representing 17.83% of the total number of students enrolled in the first year (628 students). In the next two years, there was a slightly decreasing trend as follows: in 2014 - 2015, 95 students dropped out of university, out of 600 enrolled in the first year (15.8%), and 2015-2016 the number decreased more significantly to 84 %,

compared to the last years, the number of withdrawn students being 53 out of 627 enrolled students. In the following period, 2016 -2017 there was an increase in the dropout rate of 16.6% (81 students out of 500 students enrolled in the first year). In 2017 - 2018, 66 students out of 524 (12.59%) dropped out of school. Therefore, the university aims to identify the main reasons for school dropout and find solutions to achieve the proposed target by Europe 20 project to reduce the dropout rate below 10% by the end of 2020.

The survey was developed based on a procedure that was set up by a group of experts from the E-tutoring project consortium. The data were collected through an online questionnaire, which was elaborated using a validated framework and analyzed accordingly.

Data analysis

The questionnaire was available for students on the E-tutoring project website, and the data was centralized by the project coordinator and made available to all partners. The study carried out at partnership level is much more laborious and includes the results obtained at European level, these being available free of charge and accessible on the project platform. This article presents the results obtained at the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics level, in order to identify the major requirements of students based on which recommendations will be made to improve the adaptation of students to academic life.

12 items were considered for this research:

- Q1. Gender*
- Q2. Have you ever thought about dropping out the faculty*
- Q3. Methods of teaching and evaluation*
- Q4. Personal learning difficulties*
- Q5. Personal difficulties in managing time and plans*
- Q6. Financial reasons*
- Q7. Relevance of courses for the chosen specialization*
- Q8. Perception that the degree won't be useful for accessing the world of work*
- Q9. No interest in the topics (perception of a wrong career choice)*
- Q10. Limited knowledge of the professional profiles associated with that university course*
- Q11. Lack of counselling services (tutoring services)*
- Q12. Not feeling socially included*

The sample on which the research was carried out in the university consisted of 113 students, most of them being enrolled in the first year. Of these, 68 were boys and 45 were girls (Figure 1). This result is not a limitation for research.

Fig. 1. Distribution of Gender participants

The participants' gender (Q1) is not a limitation for research.

For items Q2 - Q12 a Likert scale was used which allowed respondents to choose from a linear set of answers on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 threat “not at all” and 5 means very much. For each item analyzed calculated average, variance and standard deviation. The results obtained are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Q2 – Q12 results

ITEM	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12
Average	2.212	2.823	2.92	2.858	3.301	3.204	2.841	3.159	3.071	2.903	2.717
Variance	2.043	2.004	1.578	1.502	1.803	1.383	1.656	1.532	1.322	1.628	1.513
Standard deviation	1.429	1.416	1.256	1.226	1.343	1.176	1.287	1.238	1.15	1.276	1.23

Regarding the way in which the students evaluated the analyzed aspects, it was found that there were no significant differences according to gender.

The study of the internal consistency of the items was performed using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The MS and Error values were used to calculate the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (table 2) according to formula 1. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability of the internal consistency of a set of scale.

$$\alpha = 1 - \left(\frac{MS}{Error} \right) \quad (1)$$

Table 2. ANOVA result

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Rows	758.9992	112	6.776779	5.971499	8.09E-59	1.244463748
Columns	97.87289	10	9.787289	8.624273	1.09E-13	1.839140301
Error	1271.036	1120	1.134854			
Total	2127.908	1242				
Cronbach's Alpha			0.832538			

Based on the data in the table above, using formula 1, a value of the Alpha Cronbach's coefficient equal to 0.83 was obtained. The obtained coefficient shows that the internal consistency level in the case of the applied questionnaire is very good for using the data obtained in the data analysis. As Keith S. Taber (2018) said, the values of the Cronbach's Alpha between 0.70 and 0.90 suggest a good internal consistency in science education studies.

In order to avoid the dependence between two quantitative variables of the sample of data collected by applying the questionnaire, Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was determined. The obtained coefficients had values between -1 (perfectly negative correlation) and 1 (perfectly positive correlation). The sign of the coefficient represents the meaning of the correlation, namely: the positive value corresponds to the variations of the same meaning and the negative one to those of the opposite direction. The absolute values of the correlation coefficients, presented in table 3, express the intensity of the association between the items.

Thus, for $\alpha < 0.05$, values of the correlation coefficient from - 0.25 to 0.25 were obtained, representing a weak or zero correlation, from 0.25 to 0.50 (or from - 0.25 to -0.50) acceptable degree of association, from 0.50 to 0.75 (or from -0.50 to -0.75) very good correlation.

Table 3. Coefficients Correlation

	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12
Q2	1.00										
Q3	0.23	1.00									
Q4	0.02	0.35	1.00								
Q5	-0.06	0.35	0.54	1.00							
Q6	-0.19	0.14	0.34	0.43	1.00						
Q7	0.14	0.52	0.35	0.45	0.31	1.00					
Q8	-0.04	0.43	0.38	0.46	0.32	0.58	1.00				
Q9	0.02	0.46	0.33	0.41	0.34	0.40	0.43	1.00			
Q10	-0.01	0.34	0.46	0.48	0.27	0.46	0.40	0.53	1.00		
Q11	0.09	0.30	0.36	0.29	0.34	0.43	0.35	0.28	0.63	1.00	
Q12	0.08	0.32	0.29	0.26	0.31	0.39	0.31	0.27	0.48	0.59	1.00

As it results from the table of correlation coefficients, it is found that most correlation coefficients are positive, resulting in a direct correlation (the two correlated variables vary in the same direction) and only between perers Q2 - Q5, Q2 - Q6, Q2 - Q8, and Q2 - Q10, we have an inverse correlation, the pairs of correlated variables vary in the opposite direction (when one increases, the other decreases). A correlation coefficient of 0.63 was obtained between items *Q11. Lack of counseling services* if *Q10. Limited knowledge of the professional profiles associated with that university course*. Thus, in the students' opinion, the counseling services would help them to overcome the obstacles related to the association of the courses with their professional profile. A significant number of students consider that certain courses that they study in the first year of study, will not be useful in the profession of engineer.

As it can be seen in Table 3, there are items for which the absolute value of the correlation coefficient is weak, very close to zero. Between these variables there is a statistical link that can be taken in the analysis and interpretation of results, although the dependence is not linear.

A significant part of the students enrolled in the first year (47%) stated that they had never thought about dropping faculty (Figure 2). But, at the same time, the extreme values are not to be ignored at all, namely 12% (5 - on the Likert scale) of the analyzed sample expressed their firm intention to abandon the studies, respectively 12% (4 - on the Likert scale). The elements that leading the student to develop such thoughts are the *Methods of teaching and evaluation*.

HAVE YOU EVER THOUGHT ABOUT DROPPING OUT THE FACULTY?

Fig. 2. Studetns` opinion related to leaving faculty

As it can be seen in Figure 3, 32% of students consider that *Methods of teaching and evaluation* influences students' decision to drop out of school.

METHODS OF TEACHING AND EVALUATION

Fig. 3. Students' decision to drop out of school.

Higher averages for the analyzed factors were obtained, in decreasing order for Items ``Q6. Financial reasons`` (3,301), Q7. Relevance of courses for the chosen specialization (3,204), Q9. No interest in the topics (perception of a wrong career choice) (3,159), Q10. Limited knowledge of the professional profiles associated with that university course (3,071).

A high percentage of students prefer to work while they study. Although some of them work part time, they have difficulty finding a balance between the work schedule and the teaching activities. Most jobs are not specific to college specialization, which is why students consider certain courses irrelevant, sometimes even unnecessary. This is also reflected in the significant number of students who appreciate that certain courses are not suitable for the specialization they have chosen.

Conclusion

From the analysis of the data obtained by applying the questionnaire, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The results of this study highlighted the main needs of students. These will be the basis for formulating recommendations to reduce the phenomenon of school dropout.
- Analyzing the distribution of options expressed by students, the lack of financial resources is the main factor that contributes to increasing the dropout rate. The implementation of programs designed to support students from vulnerable groups, the provision of scholarships and part-time jobs for students supports students in maintaining their academic careers. Employment agencies set up in universities can provide the necessary support to students in choosing a job that ensures a flexible schedule, appropriate to the students' schedule.
- Difficulties that students face are related to adapting to the specifics of higher education in terms of the pace of teaching - learning and managing the volume of information. To mitigate this effect of this factor, the Ministry of National Education and Scientific Research (MENCS), through the Externally Funded Project Management Unit (UMPFE), implemented the ROSE program. Within this program, through the project "Involved students, engineers for the future! (SIMPLE) - ROSE AG 150 SGU NC II there are remedial modules complementary to the courses taught by faculty members. These modules are needed to improve students' knowledge of subjects where students' difficulties have been identified.
- The decision to drop out of college in the first year of study is also generated by the personal motivation of students. In the opinion of the students who participated in this study, the different

personalities of the students and the environment from which they come influence the development of friendships and social integration in the university environment. Tutoring and counseling activities involving teachers, year tutors, counselors and student associations can be beneficial for increasing personal satisfaction. Personal counseling sessions help students identify sensitive points, self-knowledge, and increase a sense of belonging to a group. Facilitating the transition from high school to university life and adapting students to academic life can also be supported by intensifying mentoring activities by teachers and counseling and career guidance sessions.

- In the opinion of the interviewed students, not all subjects in the school curriculum are absolutely necessary in their profession. This aspect can be improved by involving students in joint activities with employers to confirm that what they will study in courses and laboratories is useful and has applicability in the labor market. In addition, by promoting job offers by employers, students will have the opportunity to know the employment options in the field studied, thus increasing students' interest in graduating. Visits to companies can also arouse students' interest in the fields they have chosen and increase their academic performance. Internships can help students identify a job according to the field studied and in accordance with their professional aspirations and interests, thus intensifying their desire to complete their studies.
- The recommendations made in this study should be among the major concerns of higher education institutions and career counseling and guidance centers to increase the pass rate at the end of the first academic year.
- The results demonstrate the need to design and develop an innovative system, based on peer learning and the lifelong career guidance approach. Improvements in the education system can be achieved through political cooperation, benchmarking and funding programs, such as the Erasmus + program. The E-tutoring project, supported by the Erasmus + program, aims to develop an innovative system and useful tools for tutors, teachers, counselors and students to help reduce the dropout rate.

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